

FREQUENCY CONTROL OF NONLINEAR OSCILLATORS – STRATEGIES FOR REALTIME SOUND SYNTHESIS

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ABSTRACT

In sound synthesis nonlinear oscillators are used to produce sounds with rich spectra or as LFOs to produce envelopes and trajectories. The frequencies of nonlinear oscillators depend on various parameters and, in most cases, cannot be calculated. This paper presents some well-known nonlinear oscillators which have been implemented in several sound synthesis languages. It is shown how to measure the frequencies of these oscillators precisely in a fast and straightforward way. The fundamentals of feedback control are introduced and applied to the control of the frequencies of these oscillators by adapting their parameters or the time step of their simulation. For demonstration purposes the oscillators as well as the measurement and control systems have been implemented in mxj-externals for Max and provided for download from <http://www.icst.net/downloads>.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most systems used in sound synthesis and sound processing such as filters, oscillators, etc. are linear because they are stable and their behavior is predictable. Nonlinear systems, on the contrary, tend to be unstable and unpredictable. At the same time they are more flexible, interesting, and startling, and they often sound more ‘natural’ because it is a characteristic of most natural (biological, mechanical, electrical) systems not to be linear. In the last decades nonlinear systems have been studied extensively in different fields such as nonlinear dynamics or chaos theory. These investigations have become feasible due to computer-based methods. Likewise, nonlinear systems have been used in sound synthesis (see e.g. [1][2]). Early nonlinear techniques in sound synthesis such as frequency modulation, amplitude modulation, or distortion are predictable and stable, and the resulting frequencies can easily be calculated. In contrast, the frequencies of the nonlinear oscillators described in this paper depend on various parameters such as the coefficients of the differential equations, the damping, and even the amplitude. Only for the most simple nonlinear systems (e.g. a pendulum) the frequency can be calculated by a closed formula. There exist different methods to achieve approximate solutions such as perturbation theory (for a review on recently developed analytical methods see [3]). However, these methods are technically demanding and most of them are only usable for small nonlinearities. Simple methods as Ji-Huan He’s modern interpretation of an ancient Chinese mathematical method [3] as well as a modified version of it [4] are not precise enough for mu-

sical purposes because the inaccuracy of the calculated frequency reaches up to 8% which corresponds in terms of musical intervals to a deviation of more than a semitone. Only a small category of nonlinear oscillators exhibit a fixed, amplitude-independent frequency, a characteristic, known as isochronicity or isochrony [5].

Different nonlinear systems have been implemented in various sound synthesis languages. However, since their frequencies cannot be exactly calculated but result from parameters with no direct musical meaning, ‘frequency’ is never a discrete input parameter. In Csound, for example, a description in the reference manual on the opcode *lorenz* describes one parameter as “the step size used in approximating the differential equation,” and continues that this parameter “can be used to control the pitch of the systems.” For the opcode *chuap* (an implementation of the Chua-system) the manual states that the step size “can be used to more or less control pitch.” Nick Collins’ *SLUGens* pack for SuperCollider 3 is presented as “a collection of novel algorithmic sound synthesis and processing Ugens” [6]. Concerning computability Collins writes that “non-standard synthesis routines are not usually tractable analytically” and “any output frequency is hostage to the dynamics of the given system, in combination with the differential equation solver’s update rate” [6]. Even in the very simple Ugen *WeaklyNonlinear* the frequency input only affects the linear part of the oscillator.

2. OSCILLATORS

This section introduces the harmonic oscillator which is mathematically described by a linear differential equation. It will be shown how it can be implemented and how its frequency is calculated. This is followed by descriptions of some nonlinear extensions of this oscillator and explanations of systems of differential equations with periodic solutions and feedback frequency modulation.

2.1 The Harmonic Oscillator

Harmonic oscillators as ideal springs and LC resonators are described by the second order linear differential equation

$$x''(t) = -\omega^2 x(t) \quad (1)$$

where $x(t)$ is the signal value at time t (e.g. the position of the mass on a spring) and $x''(t)$ the acceleration at time t . Alternatively, the harmonic oscillators can be described as a system of two differential equations of first order

$$x'(t) = v(t) \quad \text{and} \quad v'(t) = -\omega^2 x(t) \quad (2)$$

where $x'(t)$ is the velocity. The solutions of the differential equations (1) and (2) are sinusoidal oscillations

$$x(t) = A \cdot \sin(\omega t + \varphi) \quad (3)$$

with amplitude A and frequency ω . The frequency is independent of the boundary conditions and it is especially independent of the amplitude. The amplitude A and the phase constant φ nevertheless depend on boundary (e.g. initial) conditions. This system can be used as an easy to implement and very efficient oscillator by transforming the differential equation into a difference equation, i.e. a discrete time recursive system. There are various methods to get discrete time systems, for example Euler's Method, the improved Euler's Method (or Heun's Method) or the Runge-Kutta Method. The last one is often used since it provides good results even for rather large time steps. In every method the results can be improved by shortening the time step of the simulation. To keep the code short in the presented Max-externals we have implemented the Runge-Kutta Method only in one example and otherwise used the Euler's Method. In order to implement the harmonic oscillator, we first calculate the acceleration a according to the differential equation (1) with $c = (\omega/sr)^2$. From $a = dv/dt$ and $v = dx/dt$ follows $dv = a \cdot dt$ and $dx = v \cdot dt$. We therefore increment the velocity at every time step dt by the acceleration times dt and displacement x by velocity times dt .

```
a = -c*x;
v += dt*a;
x += dt*v;
```

Taking the sample period as time step ($dt = 1$) and adding an exciting input ($in[i]$ is the i -th sample of the input buffer) we get:

```
a = -c*x;
v += a;
x += v + in[i];
```

Because of the discretization the produced frequency is not exactly ω . Substituting $x_k - x_{k-1}$ for v in the above implementation we get the discrete time system

$$x_k = (2 - c)x_{k-1} - x_{k-2} + in_k \quad (4)$$

with the transfer function

$$H(z) = 1 / (1 - (2 - c)z^{-1} + z^{-2}) \quad (5)$$

The pole of $H(z)$ yields the resonance frequency of the system. For the frequency 1000 Hz we get from the differential equation $c = 0.0202994$. If we put this value in the discrete time system the frequency yields 1000.8477 Hz.

If we introduce a damping d that is proportional to the velocity x' we get a damped resonator with the equation

$$x''(t) = -\omega^2 x(t) - d \cdot x'(t) \quad (6)$$

Still the frequency does not depend on the amplitude (while it slightly depends on the damping).

2.2 Nonlinear Extensions

There are different possibilities to expand the above simple oscillator (1, 2) nonlinearly. If e.g. the restoring force of the system is not proportional to the current displacement x but is any nonlinear function of x we get differential equations of the form $x''(t) = -f(x(t))$. If the acceleration $x''(t)$ is still in opposite direction to x (at least for large $|x|$) the system is an oscillator as for example the cubic oscillator $x(t)'' = -cx(t)^3$ or the pendulum $x(t)'' = -c \cdot \sin(x(t))$. In what follows we omit the independent variable t remembering that x is always a function of the time. Since (n-fold differentiable) functions can be approximated by polynomials we concentrate on functions of the form

$$x'' = -\omega^2 x - c_2 x^2 - c_3 x^3 - \dots - c_n x^n \quad (7)$$

The restoring forces of a linear oscillator $x'' = -0.2x$, a pendulum $x'' = -0.015\sin(x)$, and a cubic oscillator $x'' = -0.01x + 0.02x^2 - 0.04x^3$ are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Force F as function of the displacement x of a linear oscillator (dashed line), a pendulum (pointed line) and a cubic oscillator (solid line).

In section 4.1 it will be described how the amplitude can be controlled. In order to produce a certain amplitude A at the start (and at any time with the withdraw of slips) we set $x(0) = A$ and $v(0) = 0$. The kinetic energy then is 0 (because $v = 0$) and the potential energy is maximal. Thus, x is at its maximum. Fig. 2 shows measurements of the frequencies of the oscillator $x'' = -0.1x + 0.2x^2 - 0.4x^3$ depending on the amplitude $x(0)$. Because of the quadratic term neither the restoring force nor the wave form nor the frequency as function of the amplitude are symmetrical.

Figure 2. Measured frequency of the simulation of the differential equation $x'' = -0.1x + 0.2x^2 - 0.4x^3$ depending on the amplitude $x(0)$.

In another type of differential equation the acceleration x'' does not only nonlinearly depend on the displacement x but also on the velocity x' . In his attempt to explain the nonlinear dynamics of vacuum tube circuits, the Dutch electrical engineer Balthasar van der Pol derived the equation

$$x'' = -\omega^2 x + \mu(1 - x^2)x' \quad (8)$$

This equation describes a linear oscillator $x'' = -\omega^2 x$ with an additional nonlinear term $\mu(1 - x^2)x'$. When $|x| < 1$, negative damping results, which means that energy is introduced into the system. Such oscillators are called self-sustained. The following code sample shows the implementation of the Van der Pol oscillator in the Max-external *smc_VdP_LFO*.

```
a = (-c*x + mu*(1 - x*x)*v);
v += dt*a;
x += (dt*v + in[i]);
```

In all these oscillators the frequency is approximately ω if the nonlinearity is small: the pendulum oscillates nearly harmonic if the amplitude is small because $\sin(x)$ equals approximately x if x is small. The cubic oscillator and the Van der Pol oscillator reduce to the harmonic oscillator if the one of the coefficients of their nonlinear components c_2 , c_3 or μ are zero.

2.3 Systems of Differential Equations

We can use any system of differential equations with periodic orbits as oscillators. The most famous are called after their inventors: Lorenz, Rössler, Chua, or Henon. The equations of the Lorenz system are

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= a(y - x) \\ y' &= x(b - z) - y \\ z' &= xy - cz \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

the equations of the Rössler system

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= -y - z \\ y' &= x + ay \\ z' &= b + xz - cz \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

All these systems create periodic or chaotic trajectories depending on the parameter values used.

2.4 Feedback Frequency Modulation

In standard FM-technique the frequency of the carrier oscillator is modulated by a second oscillator. If we scale the output x of the carrier by bf_c/A (with frequency constant of the carrier f_c , Amplitude A and a feedback factor b) and use it as modulator of the frequency input (see Fig. 3) the output signal is distorted and its frequency is lowered. This technique is called Feedback Frequency Modulation FBFM [7].

Figure 3. Flow chart of Feedback Frequency Modulation.

Fig. 4 shows the oscillation of the above system with a growing feedback factor b .

Figure 4. Oscillation of FBFM with growing feedback factor b .

3. MEASURING FREQUENCY

In order to control the frequency of an oscillator we want to measure it as precise, as fast and at as low costs as possible.

3.1 Counting Zero Crossings

In the signals produced by the above introduced oscillators (1, 6, 7, 8) we only find two zero crossings per period. If the function in equation (6) is symmetric i.e. $f(-x) = -f(x)$ the waveforms are symmetric too and the half periods have equal length. Thus, we can count the samples n between two zero crossings and get the frequency as $sr/(2n)$. Since n is integer the half period is measured only up to a precision of $n : n-1$ (i.e. for the frequency 1000Hz the half period has the length 22.05 samples and the measured frequencies are 2004.55 and 1917.39 corresponding to $n = 22$ and $n = 23$ respectively). With linear interpolation we can improve the accuracy of the measurement clearly. The fractional part Δk between two sam-

ples (before and after a zero crossing) at times k and $k-1$ with the values x_{k-1} and x_k respectively is calculated as

$$\Delta k = x_{k-1} / (x_{k-1} - x_k). \quad (11)$$

Fig. 5 shows two sample values x_k and x_{k-1} at times k and $k-1$ with different signs i.e. before and after the zero crossing and the line crossing the k -axes at $k + \Delta k$.

Figure 5. Linear interpolation of the time Δk of a zero between two samples.

In the external *smc2018_Van_der_Pol* we count the samples of the half periods with the variable *count*. We calculate the fractional part *dk* as follows: If the current sample x and the last sample x_{d1} have different signs a zero crossing occurred and we add the fractional part Δk to the counted samples *count*, calculate the frequency and start the counting of the next half period with $-\Delta k$.

```
count++;
if(x*x_d1 < 0){
    dk = x_d1/(x_d1 - x);
    count += dk;
    fr = sr/(2*count);
    count = - dk;
}
```

In a series of 1000 measurements of a Van der Pol oscillator (implemented with the Runge-Kutta method) the minimal measured frequency was 999.822 Hz and the maximal 1000.28 Hz. Even though the acceleration of the Van der Pol oscillator is not zero at $x = 0$ the result is very precise. If the acceleration is zero at $x = 0$, as in the equations (1, 6, 7), the waveform is nearly a straight line around the zero crossing and the measurements are even better and interpolation of higher order is not required.

If the zero crossings are not even spread, as in FBFM or in the system (7) with quadratic term, we count the samples between every second zero crossing as in the following code sample of the external *smc2018_FM*.

```
if(x*x_d1 <= 0){
    count2++;
    if(count2 == 2){
        dk = x_d1 / ( x_d1 - x )
        count += dk
        fr_m = pi2*sr/count;
        count2 = 0;
        count = -dk;
    }
}
```

3.2 Counting Extrema

If the waveform has no zero crossings i.e. if the values are all negative or all positive (as the z -component of the Rössler system) and only one maximum per period occurs we can calculate the frequency of the oscillation by detecting the maxima. In addition, with this procedure we get a measure for the amplitude. With a quadratic interpolation we improve the accuracy of the measurement. For the quadratic function we need three values x_k , x_{k-1} and x_{k-2} where the maximal value is x_{k-1} . The coefficients c_i of the equation $x = c_2 k^2 + c_1 k + c_0$ are calculated by substituting the three values x_k for $k = 0, -1, -2$ into the equation. At the maximum the first derivative $2c_2 k + c_1 = 0$ and we get

$$\Delta k = -1/2 + (x_{k-1} - x_k)/(x_k - 2x_{k-1} + x_{k-2}) \quad (12)$$

Fig. 6 shows three sample values x_k , x_{k-1} and x_{k-2} at times $k = 0, -1$ and -2 where $x_k < x_{k-1} > x_{k-2}$, the quadratic function defined by the three values, the maximum of the function and the time Δk between $k = -1$ and 0 .

Figure 6. Quadratic interpolation of the time Δk of a maximum between two samples.

The following code sample stems from the external *smc2018_nonlin_osc*. We store the last two samples as x_{d1} and x_{d2} . The sample x_{d1} is the nearest sample to the maximum if it is greater than x_{d2} and x . We count the sample periods (*count*), calculate the fractional part *dk* by (12), add it to the counter, calculate the frequency, and start the counting of the next period with $-\Delta k$.

```
count++;
if((x_d1 > x_d2) && (x_d1 > x)){
    dk = .5*(-x+x_d2)/(x-2*x_d1+x_d2);
    count += dk;
    fr_m = sr/count;
    count = -dk;
}
x_d2 = x_d1; x_d1 = x;
```

3.3 Complex Oscillations

If n linear oscillators (1) are coupled the total system has n eigenfrequencies. With oscillators coupled in a chain we can simulate a string with a fundamental and $n - 1$ nearly harmonic overtones with computable frequencies [8]. If the oscillators are nonlinear as in (7) the fre-

quencies cannot be calculated and the resulting waves can have more than two zero crossings (and more than one maximum) per period. Therefore we introduce a low-pass filter before detecting the frequency. In addition, a minimum number of samples a period should contain can be defined as follows

```
if(x*x_d1 <= 0 && count > count_min) ...
```

Fig. 7 shows four quasi periods of the oscillation produced by the external *smc2018_cub_string* (to the left before and to the right after filtering). 50 nonlinear oscillators (7) are coupled all of them with $c_1 = c_3 = 0.1$. The chain was undamped, the measured frequency 152 Hz.

Figure 7. Oscillation of a chain of 50 nonlinear oscillators.

4. CONTROL

In this paragraph the concept of standard control theory is introduced and applied to the control of the frequencies of oscillators. Problems that result from the delay induced by the measurement of the frequency are discussed and the control of the frequency by exciting periodic functions and by synchronization is introduced.

4.1 Feedback Control

A feedback circuit consist of several components: The state variable, i.e. the current value of the system, is called the *controlled variable* $y(t)$, the ideal value is called the *command variable* or *set point* w . The difference between the ideal value and the current value of a system is called the *system deviation* or the *error variable* $e(t) = w - y(t)$, the value produced by the system controller is known as the *correcting variable* $u(t)$. A variable which disturbs the equilibrium of a system is called a *disturbance variable* $z(t)$. The components of a feedback circuit usually belong to one of two sub-systems: the *controller* or the *control path*, which includes all other sub-systems (sometimes referred to simply as the system).

Figure 8. Components of a feedback control circuit.

In our case the controlled variable is the frequency produced and measured by the oscillator $y = f$, the command

variable is the frequency input $w = f_{in}$ of the oscillator, and the error variable $e(t) = f_{in} - f$. The correcting variable u can be a parameter of the differential equation to be controlled as ω in (8) or a, b, c in (9) or the time step dt . The control path in our externals are the oscillators themselves. There are different types of controllers known in control theory. The elements of digital controllers are systems as filters we use in digital signal processing and their behavior can be described and calculated with the same methods. In control theory systems are rarely described by their impulse response but rather by their response to the step function s_k ($s_k = 0$ for $k < 0$ and $s_k = 1$ for $k \geq 0$), i.e. to a sudden change of the input. The graphical representation of this so-called step response is often used as an icon for the controller.

We get a simple controller using the so called integral element that is defined by the system equation

$$u_k = u_{k-1} + c \cdot e_k \tag{13}$$

In order to show the reaction of this controller on the step function we set the controlled variable equal to the correcting variable $y_k = u_k$ (i.e. there is no control path) and the command variable equal to the step function $w = s_k$.

$$u_k = u_{k-1} + c(s_k - u_{k-1}) \tag{14}$$

This element corresponds to a recursive low-pass filter. Fig. 9 shows the step response of the integral element with $c = 0.08$.

Figure 9. Step response of the integral element.

In the controller of the external *smc2018_Van_der_Pol* we use the coefficient $c_c = \omega^2$ as correcting variable (remember that ω only equals the frequency when $\mu = 0$). The coefficient calculated from the measured frequency is called c_m , the coefficient calculated from the input frequency c_{in} and the feedback factor is called fb .

```
c_c += fb*(c_in - c_m);
```

In the external *smc2018_nonlin_osc* we not only control the frequency but also the amplitude since we are interested in the change of the spectrum depending on the amplitude. Fig. 10 shows the inputs and outputs of the external. Inputs are: a number for three different controllers for the frequency (selected by the max-message

freq_control int), a toggle for the activation of the amplitude controller (message *amp_control*), the coefficients c_1 , c_2 and c_3 of the differential equation, a damping coefficient *damp*, the command variables frequency *freq* and amplitude *amp*, and the feedback factors for the frequency and the amplitude control *fb_fr* and *fb_amp* respectively. The outputs are the signals x and v of the oscillator, the measured frequency and amplitude, and the time step dt .

Figure 10. External for the cubic oscillator with its inputs and outputs.

From the coefficient c_1 the frequency can be calculated if c_2 and c_3 are zero. Otherwise the frequency not only depends on all coefficients but also on the amplitude. Since we want to preserve the ratios of the coefficients c_i we do not use the linear coefficient c_1 as correcting variable to control the frequency (as we did in the Van der Pol oscillator) but the time step dt . The measured frequency is called fr_m , the input frequency fr_{in} and the feedback factor c is called fb_{fr} . The first controller uses the same control element as our first example.

```
if(fr_cntr == 1)
    dt += fb_fr*(fr_in - fr_m);
```

This controller works well if we do not lower the command frequency fr_{in} too much and too abruptly and if the feedback factor fb_{fr} is not too high. If we abruptly lower the command frequency the correcting variable dt can become negative and the calculations fail. The problem arises from the delay produced by the measurement of the frequency. Fig. 11 shows the response of the control element to a step from 1 to 0 if the measurement of the frequency and the update of the error variable $e = fr_{in} - fr_m$ are delayed (not yet taken into account the constancy of the measured frequency during a period).

Figure 11. Oscillations and negative values in the response of the correcting variable dt on a step from 1 to 0 caused by the delay of the measured frequency.

In the second controller we avoid negative values by multiplying the correcting value u by an exponential function of the error variable and multiply the time step by u :

$$u_k = u_{k-1} \exp(c \cdot e_k) \quad (15)$$

```
if(fr_cntr == 2)
    dt *= Math.exp(fb_fr*(fr_in - fr_m));
```

Fig. 12 shows that the response of this control element to the step from 1 to 0 never becomes negative. However, it approximates 0 slower than the controller above. A larger feedback factor accelerates this approximation.

Figure 12. Response of the correcting variable dt on a step from 1 to 0.

An ordinary step response cannot be calculated because the correcting value must not be zero. We instead calculate the response to a step from 0.1 to 1. We see in Fig. 13 that the new value (1.0) is reached very quickly but the correcting value overcompensates and oscillates around 1.

Figure 13. Response of the correcting variable dt on a step from 0.1 to 1.

The greater the error $e = fr_{in} - fr_m$ the faster the above controller changes the frequencies. Therefore in controller 3 we divide the error variable by the maximum of the two variables.

$$u_k = u_{k-1} \exp(c \cdot e_k / \max(w, y)) \quad (16)$$

```
if(fr_cntr == 3)
```

```
dt *= Math.exp(fb_fr*((fr_in - fr_m)/Math.max(fr_in, fr_m)));
```

Fig. 14 shows the responses of this controller to the steps from 1 to 0, from 1 to 0.2 and from 0.05 to 1. The response never becomes negative and it approximates small values very fast.

Figure 14. Response of the correcting variable dt on steps from 0.1 to 1, from 1 to 0 and from 1 to 0.2.

Since the spectrum of the nonlinear oscillator (7) not only depends on the coefficients c_i but also on the amplitude a controller for the amplitude has been implemented in the external *smc2018_nonlin_osc*. Since the maximal positive and the absolute value of the minimal value can differ we define the ‘amplitude’ as half the difference of the maximal and minimal measured value $amp_m1 - amp_m2$ (without interpolation).

```
count++;
if((x_d1 > x_d2) && (x_d1 > x)){
    amp_m1 = x_d1;
    amp_m = 0.5*(amp_m1 - amp_m2);
}
if((x_d1 < x_d2) && (x_d1 < x)) {
    amp_m2 = x_d1;
}
}
```

The amplitude can be reduced and increased by positive and negative damping respectively. Supposing a damping proportional to the velocity we introduce it in the differential equation (7) by adding the term $-d \cdot x'$.

$$x'' = -\omega^2 x - c_2 x^2 - c_3 x^3 - d \cdot x' \quad (17)$$

We control the amplitude with the command

```
damp = fb_amp*(amp_m - amp_in);
```

If the measured amplitude amp_m is smaller than the input amplitude amp_in the damping becomes negative and the oscillation is excited.

4.2 Control with Filters

The integral element (13) corresponds to a recursive low-pass filter. Thus, we can create a control circuit using the filters implemented in every sound synthesis language. It

is crucial to use a short audio buffer (vector size in Max, control period in Csound etc.) to avoid additional delay.

4.3 Control by External Forces

If the damped linear oscillator (6) with the natural frequency ω is excited with a periodic force e.g. with a sine wave $A \cdot \sin(\omega_e t)$ with the frequency ω_e it resonates at ω_e .

$$x'' = -\omega^2 x - d \cdot x' + A \cdot \sin(\omega_e t) \quad (18)$$

The cubic oscillator with damping and external force is called Duffing oscillator.

$$x'' = -\omega^2 x - c_3 x^3 - d \cdot x' + A \cdot \sin(\omega_e t) \quad (19)$$

For certain parameter values it exhibits chaotic behavior for other values we get stable cycles. The wave form and thereby the spectrum are similar to the undamped system with the same amplitude. Thus, the frequency of some damped systems can be controlled by a periodic external force. There are however different constraints to be taken into account: The amplitude of the external force and the damping of the nonlinear system must be strong enough (but not too strong in order not to influence the spectrum) and the frequency of the nonlinear system should not differ too much from the frequency of the external force. Changings of parameters can produce chaotic behavior and it can take quite a while for the system to reach stable oscillation.

While we speak of resonance in the case of damped systems as (18) and (19) there is a phenomenon called synchronization [9] studied with so called self-sustained oscillators i.e. oscillators with an internal energy which off a typical example is the Van der Pol oscillator. The frequencies of this type of oscillators can synchronize with the frequencies of weak external forces (and several coupled self-sustained oscillators can mutually synchronize even if the coupling is weak). Therefor with a strong external force (or coupling) the frequencies of such oscillators can be controlled in a wide frequency range. The spectrum of the synchronized oscillation is only marginal affected (see *smc2018_nonlin_osc*).

4.4 Control of LFOs

Because it takes at least half a period to measure the frequency of an oscillator the above described methods are not fast enough for their use in LFOs. In order to faster control the frequency f of a system we want to use as a LFO, we can simulate an identical system with a higher frequency f_h and scale the controlled parameters of the LFO by the factor f_h/f . This strategy yields perfect results e.g. for FBFM because the reduction of the frequency caused by the feedback does not depend on the frequency itself (see Max-patch *smc_2018_FBFM*). The changes of the resulting frequency are carried out at the same rate as in the high-frequency system (the measurement of the LFO's frequency of course takes at least 1/half-period s).

This technique does not produce exact results if the nonlinearity depends on the frequency of the system as in the Van der Pol oscillator (8). Since its nonlinearity $\mu(1 - x^2)x'$ is a function of x and v , it depends on the frequency. Fig. 15 shows the two waveforms of a Van der Pol oscillator with the frequencies 50 Hz (to the left) and 500 Hz (to the right) with identical $\mu = 0.2$.

Figure 15. Waveform of a Van der Pol oscillator with frequencies 50 Hz (to the left) and 500 Hz (to the right) with identical $\mu = 0.2$.

Another problem arises when the frequency and amplitude depend on each other as in the oscillator (7). As long as the amplitudes of the high frequency test oscillator and of the LFO are identical the produced frequency of the LFO matches the input frequency very precisely even if we input a new value for the amplitude (in the external *smc2018_LFO_VdP* the deviations are less than 0.01%). However, if the amplitude is changed fast and often, the frequencies deviate more and more.

5. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Some nonlinear systems provide oscillators with rich spectra and interesting, unpredictable behavior. We showed that their frequencies can under certain conditions be controlled by simple means. However, there still remain a lot of open questions: How can further parameters be controlled, especially the amplitude? How stable are the used controllers and how do they influence the stability of the controlled systems? How can we measure the frequency sufficiently fast and precise in oscillations with an unpredictable number of zero crossings and maxima? How far can we use the introduced strategies for the frequency control of quasi-periodic oscillations and coupled systems of nonlinear oscillators? How can the control parameters automatically be adjusted?

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